

Book *of* Abstracts

SPHERIC25

19th SPHERIC World Conference

Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya UPC-BarcelonaTech

17-19 June 2025

Escola de Camins

Barcelona
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Book of Abstracts of the 19th SPHERIC World Conference

Barcelona, 17-19 June 2025

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Dr. Corrado Altomare

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SPHERIC

From Bastaixos to Researchers: building for the common good

*In 14th-century Barcelona, humble port workers known as **bastaixos** voluntarily carried heavy stones from Montjuïc to help build Santa Maria del Mar church. They did it not for fame or fortune, but as a **gift to their community**—a silent act of dedication that still stands today.*

Centuries later, that same spirit lives on in the work of those who advance knowledge and innovation—whether in universities, research centres, public institutions, or industry. Though we no longer carry stones, we carry ideas. We dedicate ourselves—often behind the scenes—to develop new tools, simulate complex phenomena, design safer systems, and improve the world around us.

*Like the bastaixos, our mission is **service**. Not to build cathedrals, but to build understanding.*

*Because true progress, then and now, is **built collectively**—stone by stone, idea by idea.*

Foreword to the 19th SPHERIC World Conference

Dear Delegate,

The Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya – BarcelonaTech and the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre were honoured to host the **19th SPHERIC World Conference** in the vibrant city of Barcelona (Spain). The event stood as the foremost international forum of 2025 dedicated to **Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH)**, bringing together researchers and practitioners to share insights, foster collaboration, and chart the future of SPH across science and industry.

SPHERIC (SPH rEsearch and engineeRing International Community) represents the dynamic, global network of SPH users. As a fully Lagrangian, meshless technique, SPH enabled the simulation of highly complex phenomena—free-surface flows, multiphase interactions, large deformations in solids, fluid–structure interaction, and more—addressing scenarios where conventional Eulerian methods often fell short.

The conference provided the global platform exclusively devoted to SPH. Leading experts delivered talks spanning theoretical advances, numerical techniques, software development, experimental validation, and real-world applications.

This edition introduced several important innovations: traditional abstracts and proceedings were replaced by **extended abstracts**, allowing authors to present their work with greater clarity and detail, and a **Special Issue** in Computational Particle Mechanics was launched, offering a high-impact platform for selected contributions.

One of the highlights was the debut of **Special Sessions**, each curated by experts to focus on emerging and high-impact SPH applications. The session on **SPH in Aerospace and Maritime Fields**, organized by Salvatore Marrone and PengNan Sun, focused on topics like sloshing in aircraft and ships, and aircraft ditching. Led by Tom De Vuyst, **Solids Mechanics** offered a compelling selection of works exploring high-strain scenarios, complex boundary conditions, and new numerical approaches for structural materials. The session on **SPH Application in Coastal Engineering**, organized by Tomohiro Suzuki, explored wave dynamics and the complex interactions between multiple bodies and sea waves in the context of coastal protection. Finally, the session on **Renewable Energy Engineering Innovations through SPH Modeling**, convened by Alejandro J. C. Crespo and Bonaventura Tagliaferro, showcased works on floating offshore wind turbines, wave energy converters, hydraulic turbines, and other renewable systems, culminating in a lively panel discussion.

It was a pleasure to welcome you and witness the continued expansion of the SPHERIC community. We sincerely thank all participants for their intellectual contributions, enthusiasm, and engagement, which made this conference a resounding success.

With gratitude,

Corrado Altomare

Chair of the Local Organizing Committee of the 19th SPHERIC World Conference

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Table of contents

Session 1: CONVERGENCE, CONSISTENCY AND STABILITY (I)	1
Talk 1.1: How to train your IMP (Implicit Mid-Point) <i>D. Duque, J. Calderon-Sanchez, J. L. Cercós-Pita, P. Eleazar-Merino</i>	
Talk 1.2: Development of Fluid Interphase Particle for particle-based multiphase flow simulation <i>N. Tsuruta, T. Gotoh, A. Khayyer, H. Gotoh</i>	
Talk 1.3: Towards h/p refinement for Weakly Compressible SPH obtained with Eulerian/Lagrangian coupling <i>F. Ricci, R. Vacondio, G. Fourtakas</i>	
Talk 1.4: δ -SPH Stabilization For ISPH Scheme <i>M. De Leffe, C. Hermange, A. Bourgoin, L. Chiron</i>	
Session 2: SOLIDS MECHANICS (SS2)	13
Talk 2.1: A first-order conservation law framework for large strain compressible solids: isothermal viscoelasticity <i>C. Hean Lee, T. Jaugielavičius, S. Boyaval, A. J. Gil, J. Bonet, D. Violeau</i>	
Talk 2.2: An enhanced SPH-based hydroelastic FSI solver with structural dynamic hourglass control <i>Y. Zhan, M. Luo, A. Khayyer</i>	
Talk 2.3: Advancing the Material Point Method for Brittle Shells in Computational Mechanics <i>M. Stilz, G. Ganzenmüller, S. Hiermaier</i>	
Session 3: HIGH-PERFORMANCE COMPUTING	21
Talk 3.1: Towards heterogeneous parallelism for SPHinXsys <i>X. Hu, A. Guarnieri</i>	
Talk 3.2: TNL-SPH: Open-source modular SPH solver for modern distributed computing platforms based on GPU accelerators <i>T. Halada, L. Beneš, J. Klinkovský, T. Oberhuber</i>	
Talk 3.3: GPU acceleration of SWIFT for heterogeneous Exascale supercomputers <i>A. Nasar, G. Fourtakas, S. Kay, B. D. Rogers, M. Schaller</i>	
Session 4: RIEMANN SOLVERS	30
Talk 4.1: Riemann based SPH with divergence cleaning <i>G. Fourtakas, R. Vacondio</i>	
Talk 4.2: A Coefficient-Free β -Velocity Formulation for Improved Riemann-Based SPH <i>M. A. Hafeez, R. Vacondio, A. English, B. D. Rogers, G. Fourtakas</i>	
Talk 4.3: An enhanced coupled ISPH-TLSPH FSI solver by a Riemann fluid-structure acceleration scheme <i>T. Gotoh, A. Khayyer, H. Gotoh</i>	
Talk 4.4: SPH modelling of water flow inside a porous medium using a Riemann based formulation <i>C. D. Sousa, G. Oger, J. Michel, D. L. Touzé, D. Violeau</i>	
Session 5: COUPLING WITH OTHER METHODS	42
Talk 5.1: Coupling of SPH and Volume-of-Fluid <i>M. Wicker, N. Bürkle, R. Koch, H. J. Bauer</i>	
Talk 5.2: A two-way ISPH-FVM coupling for two-phase flows <i>M. Helal, M. S. Shadloo, V. Moureau, M. Cailler</i>	
Talk 5.3: A coupled WCSPH-MSDEM model for combined motion of a block contact with solid-wall boundary <i>S. Gao, B. Ren, H. Wen</i>	

Talk 5.4: A coupled FV-SPH approach to simulate the flow around a vertical free-surface piercing cylinder

S. Marrone, A. Colagrossi, A. D. Mascio, D. L. Touzé

Session 6: SPH IN AEROSPACE AND MARITIME FIELDS (SS1-I)

54

Talk 6.1: Numerical simulation of long-term sloshing flows using an enhanced SPH model

M. Luo, Y. Zhan, A. Khayyer

Talk 6.2: Violent sloshing flows with thermal conduction using δ -LES-SPH

A. Colagrossi, S. Marrone, M. Antuono, J. Calderon-Sanchez, L. M. González-Gutierrez

Talk 6.3: A first isothermal approach to 3D sloshing for aircraft hydrogen tanks.

Ignacio Sánchez-Ojeda, J. Calderon-Sanchez, L. M. González-Gutierrez

Talk 6.4: A versatile SPH algorithm for multiphase pipe flow

Z. Y. Zhan, Z. Chen

Session 7

Track A: CONVERGENCE, CONSISTENCY AND STABILITY (II)

66

Talk 7.1A: Towards high-order simulation of compressible flows: insights from dispersion analysis

O.P. Stoyanovskaya, M.S. Arendarenko, O.A. Burmistrova, V.V. Grigoryev, T.V. Markelova

Talk 7.2A: Investigation on the accuracy and numerical dissipation when using the ULPH model for free-surface flows

S. X. Wu, P. N. Sun, X. T. Huang

Talk 7.3A: Pairing instability: insights and possible remedies from a local thermodynamics perspective

G. Colella, J. B. Avalos, J. P. Larentzos

Talk 7.4A: A new classification and convergence study of sph-like first and second spatial derivatives schemes

R. Fatehi

Track B: INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS IN HYDRAULICS

78

Talk 7.1B: SPH-Based Fluid-Structure Interaction to Aid Rapid Prototyping for Vehicle Water Wading

M. Make, A. Peer, S. Joshi

Talk 7.2B: Investigation of Reducing Metalworking Fluid Consumption in Deep-Hole Drilling using Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics

A. Baumann, P. Eberhard

Talk 7.3B: Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics Simulation of 3D Open Channel Flow Over Vegetated Bed

E. Chatzoglou, A. Liakopoulos

Talk 7.4B: SPH modeling for plastic transport in the nearshore zone: a laboratory-scale validation study

R. Cristofaro, A. Cappello, G. Ganci, G. Bilotta, C. Iuppa, C. Faraci

Session 8

Track A: RENEWABLE ENERGY ENGINEERING INNOVATIONS THROUGH SPH MODELING (SS4-I)

90

Talk 8.1A: A comparative study on Pelton turbines with CFD-based methods

A. Ferrarini, R. Bergamin, M. Merelli, M. Galbiati, J. M. Domínguez

Talk 8.2A: SPH chamber model towards pneumatic PTO representation for floating OWC devices

B. Mina, B. Tagliaferro, I. Martínez-Estévez, G. Malara, F. Arena, M. Gómez-Gesteira

Talk 8.3A: SPH analysis of extreme wave directionality on the dynamics of floating offshore wind turbines

S. Wang, W. L. Chuang

Talk 8.4A: Application of the SPH method to simulate coupled ionic transport and electrodeposition in lithium batteries <i>M. Morey, E. Ryan</i>	
Track B: BIOMEDICAL AND NON NEWTONIAN FLOWS	102
Talk 8.1B: SPH-Based FSI Simulations of Blood Flow in Patient-Specific Vessels with Deformable Walls <i>C. Zhao, O. J. Haidn, D. Wu, X. Hu</i>	
Talk 8.2B: Compared SPH and LBM approaches for FSI of trans-aortic flows <i>J. Lopez, M. Lallemand, J. Michel, D. L. Touzé, G. Oger</i>	
Talk 8.3B: LHMM for Rheological Analysis of Polymer Melts with DPD-SPH Coupling <i>E. A. Patiño-Nariño, N. Moreno, M. Ellero</i>	
Talk 8.4B: Coupled SPH Model for Prosthetic Valve Induced Thrombus Formation <i>S. Laha, G. Fourtakas, P. K. Das, A. Keshmiri</i>	
Session 9	
Track A: ASTROPHYSICS	114
Talk 9.1A: Protoplanetary Disc Evolution in Binary Systems: A Combined SPH and Radiative Transfer Study <i>P. P. Poblete</i>	
Talk 9.2A: In-Situ Visualization and Analysis for SPH Simulations <i>J. M. Favre, J. G. Piccinali, R. Cabezón</i>	
Talk 9.3A: Semi-confined supernovae in Giant Molecular Clouds and their impact on the interstellar medium <i>C. S. C. Lau, I. A. Bonnell</i>	
Track B: SPH IN AEROSPACE AND MARITIME FIELDS (SS1-II)	121
Talk 9.1B: Towards High-Fidelity Simulation of Compressible Flows Using Adaptive Resolution SPH <i>N. Villodi, P. Ramachandran</i>	
Talk 9.2B: SPH-based modelling of ships and ocean platforms operating in extreme environments <i>M. S. Islam</i>	
Talk 9.3B: Simulation of ship dynamics and structural response based on SPH <i>C. Ma, M. Oka</i>	
Session 10: BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	130
Talk 10.1: Pair-particle dispersion in two dimensional SPH <i>D.D. Meringolo, S. Servidio, C. Meringolo, F. Aristodemo, P.G.F. Filianoti, P. Veltri, V. Carbone</i>	
Talk 10.2: On the consistency of the SPH gradient with a Boundary Integral Method for solid wall modelling <i>V. Degand, J. Michel, D. L. Touzé, G. Oger</i>	
Talk 10.3: Wall boundary condition for the unconditionally stable SPH <i>J. L. Cercós-Pita, P. Eleazar-Merino, D. Duque, J. Calderón-Sánchez</i>	
Talk 10.4: Towards oscillation-free spectral ISPH scheme with high-order wall boundary conditions <i>M. Lin, G. Fourtakas, B. D. Rogers</i>	
Session 11	
Track A: SPH APPLICATION IN COASTAL ENGINEERING (SS3-I)	142
Talk 11.1A: SPH modelling of submarine debris flow and turbidity currents transition and FSI processes <i>D. Feng, C. Yi</i>	

Talk 11.2A: Enhancing breaking wave impact predictions on vertical piles: about the influence of dissipation terms in SPH momentum equation

C. Altomare, Y. P. Li

Talk 11.3A: An enhanced inlet boundary condition for stable and accurate nonlinear wave simulations

T. Kanehira, S. Draycott, B. D. Rogers, P. Stansby

Talk 11.4A: A generalized boundary condition for generating wave–current coupling flows in a 3D numerical tank

H. G. Lyu, P. N. Sun

Track B: ADVANCED NUMERICAL STRATEGIES FOR FREE SURFACE FLOWS **154**

Talk 11.1B: Application of Localized Implicit Iterative Particle Shifting on Free Surface Flows

M. A. Ghazi, R. Vacondio, J. C. Marongiu

Talk 11.2B: – A high accurate meshless method for free surface flows

J. M. Ortiz de Urbina, L. Ramírez

Talk 11.3B: The pressure signal in simulations of weakly compressible SPH

G. Lipari

Talk 11.4B: Framework for uncertainty quantification of wave-structure interaction in a flume

X. Luo, A. Revell, G. Fourtakas, A. B. Harish

Session 12

Track A: SPH APPLICATION IN COASTAL ENGINEERING (SS3-II) **166**

Talk 12.1A: Constrained fluid-debris impacts onto non-rigid structures in extreme hydrodynamic events using DUALSPHYSICS+CHRONO

G. Ruffini, P. D. Girolano, R. Briganti, A. D. Iasio, N. Goseberg, J. Stolle, I. Martínez-Estévez, B. Ghiassi

Talk 12.2A: Stability of tetrapod mound breakwaters against solitary waves using the SPH method

I. Martínez-Estévez, A.J.C. Crespo, J.M. Domínguez, M. Gómez-Gesteira, B. Tagliaferro, T. Suzuki, C. Altomare, S. Capasso, W. Suwannarat, J. Mitsui, S. Kubota

Talk 12.3A: Comparative Analysis of 3D Flood Dynamics under Extreme Wave Overtopping Conditions Using Lagrangian and Eulerian Approaches

J. Yoo, G. Jeong, B. Kim

Talk 12.4A: Extending the Frontiers of Coastal Engineering: Real-World Applications of DualSPHysics to Breakwaters and Quays

A. Marzeddu, C. Altomare

Track B: MACHINE LEARNING **178**

Talk 12.1B: Can Machine Learning Bridge the Gap Between Lagrangian Mesh-Free Methods and High-Order Interpolants?

L. G. Starepravo, J. King, G. Fourtakas, A. Harish, S. Lind

Talk 12.2B: MoriNet: A Machine Learning-based Mori-Zwanzig Perspective on Weakly Compressible SPH

R. Winchenbach, N. Thuerey

Talk 12.3B: Autoencoders for Lagrangian Computational Fluid Dynamics

J. O' Connor

Session 13

Track A: SPH IN AEROSPACE AND MARITIME FIELDS (SS1-III) **187**

Talk 13.1A: Rapid Variable Resolution Particle Initialization for Complex Geometries

N. Villodi and P. Ramachandran

Talk 13.2A: An efficient SPH model for the simulation of water-dropping from airtankers

X. S. Guan, P. N. Sun, X. T. Huang

Talk 13.3A: A nesting strategy to model a propeller jet wake on a scoured bathymetry using SPH

D. Ferraro, R. Gaudio, F. Aristodemo, J. M. Domínguez, A. Lauria, C. Altomare

Track B: Renewable Energy Engineering Innovations through SPH Modeling (SS4-II)

196

Talk 13.1B: Design of a Generic Chrono Framework for Fluid-Solid Interaction

R. Serban, L. Bakke, H. Unjhawala, D. Negrut

Talk 13.2B: A design tool for flexible wave energy converters based on SPH

S. Capasso, I. Martínez-Estévez, M. Göteman, J. M. Domínguez, M. Gómez-Gesteira, C. Altomare, G. Viccione, A. J. C. Crespo

Talk 13.3B: DualSPHysics validation for fluid-structure interaction with floating flexible structure in a sloshing tank environment

F. Bernardo, M. Brito, R. M.L. Ferreira, J. Leal, I. Martínez-Estévez

Session 14: SURFACE TENSION, VISCOSITY AND TURBULENCE

205

Talk 14.1: Drop coalescence and break-up through the RHOD-SPH

M. Antuono, S. Marrone, A. Colagrossi

Talk 14.2: A multi-physics single-phase SPH scheme to simulate droplet migration on a heated solid surface

C. Cen, G. Fourtakas, B. D. Rogers, S. J. Lind, A. English

Talk 14.3: Investigation of wall functions in SPH for turbulent flow modelling

A. English, R. Vacondio

Talk 14.4: Capturing violent and turbulent sloshing dynamics using SPH modelling

C. Pilloton, A. Colagrossi, H. G. Lyu, P. N. Sun

Session 15: ADAPTIVITY

217

Talk 15.1: Adaptive particle refinement for compressible smoothed particle hydrodynamics

D. J. Price, R. Nealon

Talk 15.2: Extension of the RHOD-SPH framework: towards a fully Adaptive Particle Refinement technique

J. Michel, G. Oger, S. Marrone, A. Colagrossi, D. Le Touzé

Talk 15.3: Variable resolution SPH with a Local Time Stepping procedure

F. Ricci, R. Vacondio, A. Tafuni

Capturing violent and turbulent sloshing dynamics using SPH modelling

C.Pilloton, A.Colagrossi
 Institute of Marine Engineering
 CNR-INM,
 Via di Vallerano 139, 00128, Rome, Italy
 chiara.pilloton@cnr.it, andrea.colagrossi@cnr.it

Hong-Guan Lyu, Peng-Nan Sun
 School of Ocean Engineering and Technology
 Sun Yat-sen University
 Zhuhai, 519000, China
 hongguanlyu@163.com, sunpn@mail.sysu.edu.cn

I. INTRODUCTION

In this study, five different smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) models are used to test the capability of addressing the challenges of violent sloshing flows characterized by high free-surface fragmentation and turbulent behavior. A Large Eddy Simulation (LES) framework is adopted for all five models. The comparative analysis demonstrates the improved performances for the last model which adopts the combination of renormalized pressure gradient, particle shifting technique, and an adaptive numerical diffusive term added only on the continuity equation. This combination is labeled as δ^* -SPH and the main advantages include: (i) the resolution of small-scale turbulence, (ii) a more accurate assessment of sloshing energy dissipation, (iii) a reduction in volume conservation errors, and (iv) the absence of tensile instability, establishing it as a robust scheme for studying highly turbulent sloshing flows.

II. BRIEF RECALL OF THE SPH MODELS ADOPTED

The Navier-Stokes equations for weakly-compressible liquid are discretized within a Quasi-Lagrangian SPH model as below:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\rho_i}{dt} &= -\rho_i \langle \text{div}(\mathbf{u}_i + \delta\mathbf{u}_i) \rangle + \langle \text{div}(\rho_i \delta\mathbf{u}_i) \rangle + \mathcal{D}_i^\rho \\ \rho_i \frac{d\mathbf{u}_i}{dt} &= \langle \nabla p \rangle_i + \mathbf{F}_i^V + \mathbf{f}_i + \langle \text{div}(\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}_i) \rangle + \mathcal{D}_i^{\rho\mathbf{u}} \\ \frac{d\mathbf{r}_i}{dt} &= \mathbf{u}_i + \delta\mathbf{u}_i, V_i(t) = m_i / \rho_i(t), p_i = c_0^2 (\rho_i - \rho_0), \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\langle \nabla p \rangle_i$, \mathbf{F}_i^V and \mathbf{f}_i are, respectively, the pressure, the viscous and the body forces acting on the particle i and \mathcal{D}_i^ρ and $\mathcal{D}_i^{\rho\mathbf{u}}$ are the numerical diffusivity terms adopted to stabilize the scheme (see *e.g.* [1]). The formulation of the terms $\langle \nabla p \rangle_i$, \mathcal{D}_i^ρ and $\mathcal{D}_i^{\rho\mathbf{u}}$ changes with the selected numerical scheme, as described in the following text. The viscous forces are evaluated with a sub-grid model and are described in detail in [2]. The vector $\delta\mathbf{u}$ is the shifting velocity related to the Particle Shifting Technique (PST) adopted to regularize the spatial distribution of the particles during their motion. Since the particles are moving with modified velocity $(\mathbf{u} + \delta\mathbf{u})$ and the above equations are written in an Arbitrary-Lagrangian-Eulerian framework. For this reason, the continuity, and the momentum equations contain terms with spatial derivatives of $\delta\mathbf{u}$. The specific law chosen

for $\delta\mathbf{u}$ is the same reported in [3]. The smoothed divergence operators of (1) are given in [4]. The spatial gradients are approximated through convolution summations with a kernel function W_{ij} . A C2-Wendland kernel is adopted in the present work.

A. Pressure forces model

Regarding the smoothed pressure gradient, two different approaches are considered:

$$\begin{cases} \langle \nabla p \rangle_i^C &= \sum_j (p_i + p_j) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \langle \nabla p \rangle_i^L &= \mathbb{L}_i \sum_j (p_j - p_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbb{L}_i is the renormalization tensor (see *e.g.* [1]).

The first smoothed operator $\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^C$ is classically used in the conservative SPH models (see *e.g.* [5]). The smoothed operator $\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^L$ can reproduce linear function, therefore is more accurate than $\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^C$ and it avoids the so-called tensile instability [6]. However, it is quite sensible to the particles' spatial distribution. To avoid ill-conditions for the tensor \mathbb{L} , $\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^L$ can be used only far enough to the free-surface region, and particle shifting is mandatory for practical applications. For this reason, a third smoothed operator is defined as:

$$\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^* = \begin{cases} \langle \nabla p \rangle_i^L & \text{if } i \in \mathcal{I} \text{ \& } \Gamma_i \geq 0.95 \\ \langle \nabla p \rangle_i^C & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where the subset \mathcal{I} consists only of the inner fluid particles, *i.e.* those particles whose kernel support does not intersect the free surface. For this purpose, it is necessary to identify the particles belonging to the free-surface [7]. Finally, the second condition $\Gamma_i := \sum_j W_{ij} V_j > 0.95$ ensures that particles belonging to free surfaces that approach each other during liquid impact events are not seen as interior particles.

B. Diffusive terms

It is well known in the literature that the SPH schemes need to be stabilized by introducing numerical dissipation to avoid an extremely noisy pressure field. A traditional way to achieve stabilization is using a Riemann solver to evolve the solution in time. In particular, in this work, the model described in [8] was

followed, where the mass of the particles does not vary in time and the acoustic approximation is adopted with a slope limiter considered through a MUSCL (Monotone Upstream Scheme for Conservation Laws) procedure to increase the order of the scheme (see [3]). A simplified version of the Riemann-SPH is the so-called δ -SPH proposed by [9] and extended in the LES framework in [10] where only a diffusive term is added to the continuity equation.

C. The considered five SPH models

Five SPH schemes are considered in the present work. The differences between those models are recalled in Table I based on the use or not of the PST and the presence of not of numerical diffusive terms, and finally which formula is embedded for the pressure forces. The δ^* -SPH is the novel model proposed in the

	PST	\mathcal{D}_i^p	$\mathcal{D}_i^{\rho u}$	$\langle \nabla p \rangle_i$
Standard SPH	NO	0	0	$\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^C$
δ -SPH	NO	$\Theta_{i,\delta}^p$	0	$\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^C$
Riemann-SPH	NO	$\Theta_{i,Rie}^p$	$\Theta_{i,Rie}^{\rho u}$	$\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^C$
RHOD-SPH	YES	$\Theta_{i,Rie}^p$	$\Theta_{i,Rie}^{\rho u}$	$\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^*$
δ^* -SPH	YES	$\Theta_{i,\delta}^p$	0	$\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^*$

TABLE I
THE FIVE SPH MODELS CONSIDERED.

present work. In the next section, it will be shown that it is the one that presents the best results also in terms of the solution of the vorticity field.

D. Evaluation of the slosh dissipation

The energy balance in the noninertial frame of reference (NiFoR) moving with the tank is :

$$[\mathcal{E}_K + \mathcal{E}_P](t) - [\mathcal{E}_K + \mathcal{E}_P](t_0) - \mathcal{W}_{NF} = Q_V + Q_N \quad (4)$$

On the left-hand side of Eq. (4), \mathcal{E}_K and \mathcal{E}_P are the kinetic and potential energy and \mathcal{W}_{NF} is the work related to the non-inertial forces. Conversely, the right-hand side of the energy balance (4) includes both the dissipation due to the real and turbulent viscosity Q_V , while Q_N is the numerical dissipation taking into account the effect of the numerical diffusion terms and the particle displacement $\delta \mathbf{u}$. The numerical dissipation is not negligible during fluid impact events, where mechanical energy is converted to compressible energy, which is dissipated by the numerical diffusion terms. Following [11], it can be decomposed as:

$$Q_V = Q_\omega + \mathcal{E}_{FS}, \quad Q_\omega := - \int_{t_0}^t \int_{\Omega} (\mu + \mu_T) \|\nabla \times \mathbf{u}\|^2 dV dt. \quad (5)$$

where Q_ω is the dissipation power due to enstrophy while \mathcal{E}_{FS} is a power related to the viscous deformation of the fluid domain Ω due to the movement of the free surface.

III. TEST-CASE DESCRIPTION

The present study examines violent heave sloshing flow in a partially filled rectangular tank through tests and numerical simulations using single-phase SPH models. This test case was also investigated experimentally (described in detail in [12]). The tank measures L , D and W cm and is filled to 50% of its volume, $H = D/2$, with water. Experimentally, the tank is mounted on six springs, oscillating at a frequency of $f_0 = 6.51$ Hz with an exponentially decreasing amplitude over 25 cycles due to friction and slosh dissipation. The maximum vertical displacement is $2A = 1.14L$. The sloshing flow persists longer due to the high Reynolds number, see [13]. Intense oscillations cause significant deformation and fragmentation of the free surface and turbulent flow (see Figure 1). The reference energy is set as $\Delta E = \rho LHW(A\Omega)^2/2$, where $\Omega = 2\pi f_0$. The experiments were numerically simulated using a single-phase SPH solver, which aligned well with the experimental data ([3], [13]).

Fig. 1. Snapshots of the experimental campaign, see [12]

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 illustrates the vorticity field computed using the δ^* -SPH model, at the maximum spatial resolution $N = H/\Delta r = 800$, at time $t = 3.52T$, corresponding to the most energetic phase of the flow. Multiple scales of vorticity are evident, with distinct eddies generated by the reconnection of the free surface as the tank descends.

The time histories of the enstrophy dissipation Q_ω evaluated by five different models are shown in Figure 3. This plot highlights the capability of the δ^* -SPH model to accurately capture this dissipation component, which remains consistently smaller in magnitude when computed with other SPH formulations.

Finally, Figure 4 presents the time histories of total slosh dissipation as predicted by the δ^* -SPH model in both 2D and 3D frameworks. In the 3D case, the comparison with the experimental data of [12] demonstrates excellent agreement, validating the effectiveness of the proposed model in handling violent free-surface flows. The same figure also shows that the dissipation estimates obtained in the 2D framework are remarkably close to the experimental data, despite the pronounced three-dimensional nature of the turbulent flow under investigation.

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Fig. 2. δ^* -SPH vorticity (top) and eddy viscosity (bottom) fields at time $t = 3.52T$.

Fig. 3. Enstrophy slosh dissipation, comparison between the different SPH models.

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Fig. 4. δ^* -SPH slosh dissipation in 2D and 3D framework, comparison with the experimental data by [12].

by Siemens Digital Industries Software.

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